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Автор:

Собирова Башорат Баходировна, старший преподаватель кафедры Русского языка и литературы Гулистанского государственного университета.

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THE PROBLEM OF DEFINING THE TERM “SCIENCE FICTION” AND SPECIFYING ITS ESSENTIAL PROPERTIES

ILMIY FANTASTIKASIGA TA’RIF BERISH VA UNING MUHIM XUSUSIYATLARINI ANIQLASH MUAMMOSI

ПРОБЛЕМА ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ТЕРМИНА НАУЧНАЯ ФАНТАСТИКА И ВЫЯВЛЕНИЕ ЕЁ ОСНОВНЫХ СВОЙСТВ

Akhmedov Rafael Sharifovich

Gulistan State University, 120100. 4th-microregion, Gulistan City, Syrdarya region.

E-mail: rapha84@mail.ru

Abstract. The article reveals some controversial issues concerning science fiction and tries to solve the problem of the term definition. Any discussion of science fiction or its nature began with definitions, but the disparate characteristics of its constituent elements is one of the reasons that the genre is so difficult to define and so hard to distinguish from other categories of fiction. The focus of the article is on how “science fiction” can be defined in a way that reflects the most characteristic features of the genre.

Key words: science fiction, speculative fiction, Asimov, genre.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada ilmiy fantastikaga oid ayrim munozarali masalalar ochib beriladi va “ilmiy fantastika” atamasiga ta’rif berish muammosi yechiladi. Ilmiy-fantastika yoki uning tabiati haqida har qanday muhokama ta’riflar bilan boshlanadi, lekin uning tarkibiy elementlar bir-biriga o’xshamagan xususiyatlariga ega, shuning uchun janrga ta’rif berish va uni boshqa badiiy toifalaridan farqlash juda qiyin. Maqolaning diqqat markazida "ilmiy-fantastik" janrga eng xarakterli xususiyatlarini aks ettiradigan ta’rif berishdir.

Kalit so’zlar: ilmiy-fantastika, spekulyativ adabiyoti, Azimov, janr.

Аннотация. В статье раскрываются некоторые спорные моменты, касающиеся научно-фантастической литературы и решается проблема определения термина «научная фантастика». Любые обсуждения о научной фантастике или её природе начинаются с определения, но несхожие свойства составляющих её элементов являются причиной того, почему данный жанр так проблематично определить и тяжело отделить от других литературных категорий. Статья нацелена на то, как определить научную фантастику таким образом, чтобы отразить все особенные черты данного жанра.

Ключевые слова: научная фантастика, литература размышлений, Азимов, жанр.

Introduction. There is no branch in literature as dynamic and diversified as science fiction. Science fiction, as an independent literary genre, is at the intersection of numerous fields. It is a literature which draws on popular culture, and which engages in speculation about science, history and all types of social relations. Science fiction is the field which is subject to constant change and progress with regard to the great changes in the modern society, the rapid technological

developments and the revolutionary scientific inventions in the modern world and their impact on humanity. For many critics and academics, science fiction is problematic in the sense that the genre that depicts worlds which are different from our own, as for instance in stories set in the future or on other planets, and that uses a wide range of topics, motifs and elements, raises the question of how science fiction is to be defined, and how it has come to exist. This article provides various definitions given to science fiction; it surveys its diverse themes and image-systems (elements); and traces its nature before it has become an independent genre of literature. Since the writing of science fiction has entailed some change and modification of the established conventions of fiction writing, there have been many attempts at establishing a practical and convenient definition that might be consistent and concordant with its nature.

Method. The research methodology was based on bringing together opinions of scholars and practitioners of science fiction, which looked at the genre from different angles. There were different ways of coming at the matter of formulating proper definition of a cultural phenomenon, or collection of texts, called “science fiction” and the study attempted to approach the matter from a variety of different perspectives, introducing and discussing a number of critical approaches to science fiction. From the wider variety of materials available, the most recent and influential had been chosen. The results of the analysis showed that in spite of various opinions, there was much wider agreement among scholars about the shape of this genre: descriptions of science fiction under review shared a common core of three criteria held characteristic of this literary kind, namely its non-realism, its unambiguous (global) semantic coherence (plausibility) and the presence of science in the widest sense as a dominant thematic element. The article concluded with a definition of “science fiction” formulated on the basis of the overview and analysis results. Thus, the research question of the article is how to define the term “science fiction” taking into consideration the nature and all basic characteristics of this literary genre.

Research Design. According to the author’s hypothesis, the more investigations, researches and opinions are taken into account, the more correct and universal definition can be found out. Therefore, for the purposes of this research, the author chose the interpretivist approach, rather than the pragmatist approaches, because abstract, non-quantifiable variables such as “culture”, “literature”, comparing “science fiction” with “hard science fiction” and analyzing whether performing techniques and their application into literature can have positive influence on practice were part of the objectives of the research. For the purposes of this research, the author has decided to use a combination of two classic philological sciences’ research tools – documentary analysis and literature review. Documentary analysis involves obtaining data from existing documents (about 30 scientific articles and theses) without having to question people through interview, questionnaires or observe their behavior. Documentary analysis is the main way that linguists obtain data about their research subjects (which is mostly written), but it can also be a valuable tool for contemporary social scientists. This research combines elements of linguistic, philological and social sciences, that is why documentary analysis turns out to be the most effective and objective. Documents helped to reveal a great deal about the topic of the article. Some documents are part of the public domain and are freely accessible, whereas other documents may be classified, confidential or otherwise unavailable to public access. In case when such documents were used as data for the research, the researcher came to an agreement with the holder of the documents about how the contents can and cannot be used and how confidentiality will be preserved.

Results and Discussion. Since the recognition of science fiction (SF) as an independent genre of literature, its authors and critics vied to clearly and consistently formulate the difference between this genre and other genres of fantastic literature. In general, all science fiction writers and theorists of the genre realized that the signification of such texts is possible mainly when referring to the scientific discourse.

The emphasis of the theory of science fiction on “scientific nature”, “sciolism”, and even on the “para-scientific” content (regardless of the decision on the definition of the specificity of expression), seems to solve the problem of definition. Meanwhile, there are more than a dozen definitions of “science fiction”. The most famous definitions were suggested by Basil Davenport, Kingsley Amis, Mark Rose, etc. The wittiest, though largely incorrect, definition was given by Rodman Edward “Rod” Serling: “fantasy is impossible, which became probable, and science fiction is incredible, which became possible.” [12] At first glance, it seems to be a good functional definition. But simplicity of this definition provokes an insidious ambiguity leading to confusion of concepts. Indeed, what is meant by “impossible”, “probable”, “incredible” or “possible”? [4]

Most of the definitions given by critics and science fiction writers, from the 1920s to the 1960s, boils down to the fact that it is literature extrapolating science, and this distinguishes it, for example, from fantasy. Similar definition was given by John Campbell. But Basil Davenport concretized this definition, insisting on “extrapolation of a certain trend in social development.” [7] The same idea was suggested by Isaac Asimov, who proposed to distinguish between “socially fantastic” (social-philosophical) and “strictly scientific” (hard) science fictions, as the basis of the former are social sciences, while the basis of the latter are natural sciences. In some critical essays, Isaac Asimov argues that modern science fiction as a whole is a “social experiment on paper.” [5]

The classical era of science fiction was characterized by attempts to achieve the purity of the genre, not mixed with Gothic elements or household esotericism. The biggest difficulty is the distinction between science fiction and utopia: best

examples of that are works of Herbert George Wells and Aldos Huxley. This complexity is predetermined by a number of circumstances: on the one hand, utopia is a more ancient genre, and therefore science fiction inherits many features of it, and secondly, the range of utopia is at the same time wider and narrower comparing to the range of science fiction. For example, according to Samuel Durham Cooper, any science fiction text tells readers about “utopia”, about “nowhere”, i.e. about a non-existent locus [6]. Building a hypothetical future or an alternative present (parallel worlds, etc.), science fiction usually takes into account sociality and statehood – exactly what is the prerogative of all utopias except individualistic ones. And even in the latter ones – social context is presented by default.

Darko Suvin made a radical breakthrough in the problem of definition, calling science fiction “the literature of cognitive estrangement”. Estrangement, in this case, is an accentuation of any element in the text of a literary work in order to cause the perception of it in unusual and uncommon associations. Now this definition of Darko Suvin enjoys universal recognition because of its capacity and apparent consistency. Darko Suvin defined science fiction as “a literary genre or verbal construct whose necessary and sufficient conditions are the presence and interaction of estrangement and cognition.” [13].

In the works of the 1970 s, including his collection “Metamorphoses of Science Fiction” (1979), Darko Suvin explains his definition and among the identifiable and essential taxonomic features of science fiction puts “strange newness” or “novum” in the first place. Estrangement, i.e. the method of creating a new coordinate system that corresponds to the traditional one, is in the second place. The term “estrangement” is borrowed, as Darko Suvin underlines, from Viktor Shklovsky and Bertolt Brecht. Moreover, estrangement is considered to be both “scientific” (cognitive) instrument and “artistic” technique [14]. The formal structure of science fiction is based on the estrangement as on an artistic technique, thanks to which the radical change (object or phenomenon) is presented in such a way that it is perceived as both the unknown and the known. Unlike myth and other fantastic (“non-cognitive”) genres, science fiction emphasizes the need to clarify the unknown novelty, to solve the mystery behind the Change. Thus, science fiction not only depicts, but also problematizes, calls for a rational, analytical understanding of both the nature of the amazing reality and the nature of the “zero” or “naturalistic” reality, i.e. the one that surrounds the author of science fiction text. As a result, Darko Suvin emphasizes that in science fiction “the cognitive element, which is really scientific in most cases, becomes a measure of aesthetic quality of a science fiction book and a source of specific pleasure for a reader.” [13]

In “Science Fiction and the Genealogical Jungle” Darko Suvin also supported his argument with detailed evidence of inconsistency of adjacent and neighboring fantasy genres to the above criteria. He “accused” mimic SF-texts in breach of contract of the author with the reader trapped in an alternate world “infected” by fantasy realia such as witches, because the text of this kind has the features of fabulous taxonomy. The reality represented in such a hybrid text is not intended for rational (cognitive) reading [15] James Gunn and Matthew Candelaria included two texts of Darko Suvin in their anthology [9] and consider these two texts as fundamental and therefore not requiring critical or polemical accompaniment.

“Cognition”, with its rational, logical implications, refers to that aspect of science fiction that prompts us to try and understand, to comprehend, the alien landscape of a given science fiction book, film or story. “Estrangement” is a term from Brecht, more usually rendered in English-language criticism as “alienation”; in this context it refers to that element of science fiction that we recognize as different, that “estranges” us from the familiar and every day. If the science fiction text were entirely concerned with “estrangement”, then we would not be able to understand it; if it were entirely to do with “cognition”, then it would be scientific or documentary rather than science fiction. According to Darko Suvin, both features need to be present; and it is this copresence that allows science fiction both relevance to our world and the position to challenge the ordinary, the taken-for-granted. The main “formal device” of Suvin’s version of science fiction is the novum [10].

In fact, even in the Arab world, “science fiction took the form of travel writings, or cosmographical treatises that earnestly engaged with the extraordinary and the occult. The literature like that was called the “ajaib” literature... ranged from expositions on natural phenomena or extraordinary human feats of a semi-mythic stature to mariners’ tales and folkloric material.” [2] It seems that the term “science fiction” should be used to denote such texts in which “cognitive estrangement” is not just present, but is a dominant feature. Moreover, “cognition” and “estrangement” of scientific and technological progress or regression (at least in hard science fiction) should also be considered the dominant features of science fiction. Otherwise, the “cognitive effect” of the texts about elves or werewolves will be equated to the “cognitive effect” produced by the texts about time machine, and, as a result, it will lead to the loss of recognizable outlines of genre boundaries. Many literary critics, including Donald Hassler, Scott Green, Sergei Bereznoy and others, believe that for Isaac Asimov, science fiction is not just another, exceptionally popular literary genre, but a kind of speculative sociology. Science fiction should systematically investigate possible ways of social development, warn about dangerous trends and, most importantly, make rational thinking about the destiny of humanity. Thus, the growing popularity of this genre of literature in our age only increases the moral and social responsibility of writers [1].

Beginning from the middle of the 20th century a new approach in literary criticism was worked out to study historical and literary connections of science fiction, its artistic principles, the historical variability of the fantastic images.

Some critics, including Moravec, Sawyer, Brandis, Dmitrievskiy, Dneprov, historian Carl Hempel and others, consider ancient myths and legends as first forms of science fiction. These researchers form so-called “First group”. “Second group” is represented by James Gunn, Roger Clark, Vitaliy Karatsupa, Eugene Parnov, Yulia Batalina. They refer to the first works of SF purely technical reference books by Hugo Gernsback and space adventures by Edgar Burroughs [3].

The thesis about the Otherness, although it helps to distinguish between different fantastic genres, but somewhat ignores the problem of fictionality. Indeed, it is the prerogative of any literary text, not necessarily fantastic, to create alternative reality. The question of fictionality was clarified, in particular, by Umberto Eco in his “Six Walks in the Fictional Woods” (Eco, 1998) and by Wolfe Schmid in his “Narratology.” [11] But, one way or another, it should be confirmed that science fiction has its own specific alternative reality, the Otherness, which we propose to call “the Otherness within the reason” or “rationally represented Otherness.”

Looking at the vast horizons of science fiction and its mostly “conditional” boundaries, as it is proved by both criticism and fiction itself, let us ask the following question: are there a text that could serve as an example of a perfect and pure embodiment of science fiction, possessing exclusively science fiction pragmatics and poetics, i.e. correct taxonomy? We suppose that such texts can be found. Perfect science fiction text should have proportionality, cognitive value, streamlined otherness, and demonstrate the cognition of the depicted world.

Conclusion. To conclude, most definitions involve the aspect of science and technology which is associated directly with the genre although it may sometimes appear as pseudo-science or pseudo-technology. For many years since the genre has been labelled “science fiction”, writers and critics have argued about a working definition that might embody its specific characteristics and its particularity. Nevertheless, science is not the whole bulk of science fiction writing; indeed, we are faced with a heterogeneous genre that combines multiple elements from the real to the purely unreal and imaginative. For this reason, it is always very difficult to define science fiction with one simple, straightforward definition that clarifies its nature and its relation to other genres since science fiction overlaps with other branches of literature, especially with fantasy. The complexity of science fiction does not only lie in its definition but also in its various categories or sub-genres that have come to exist along with the extraordinary progress in scientific and technological research and knowledge. Finally, we propose an adjusted definition of science fiction based on the summary results of the above-described critical debates: *science fiction is the literature of cognitive estrangement, which rationally represents strange, but known world, which is different in relation to the world surrounding the author and extrapolated to the new reality of the radical changes deriving from scientific and technical progress or regress.*

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Author:

Akhmedov Rafael Sharifovich – Senior Lecturer, Researcher, Gulistan State University.

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